

**CRITICAL REVIEW OF DRINKING MOTIVES BETWEEN SOCIAL ANXIETY AND
ALCOHOL USE**

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ABSTRACT

Drinking alcohol becomes a trend when social fear becomes a threat. The relaxing effect of alcohol on the central nervous system, its unconstrained and empowering effects of social impulses, and its perceived beneficial or recovery action on physical and emotional pain are often suggested as reasons why people begin and maintain their drinking behavior, despite knowing its abuse, potential side effects, and medium-to long-term ill effects on health. The purpose of this review is to address the role of drinking motives in predicting alcohol use among normal and socially anxious population and its mediating effect in the relationship between social anxiety and alcohol use. Variables analyzed included prevalence, gender, personality trait, drinking motives, and self-medication hypothesis. Through this paper, a brief understanding gained into how people with and without social anxiety caters their fear to events that challenges their social image. It is highly suggestible that social anxiety has a positive relationship with alcohol use; which mediated by drinking motives, particularly, social, conformity and coping motives. Self-medication hypothesis too were found to be playing a major role in predicting alcohol consumption, especially among people who were tending to drink to cope with unpleasant emotions both before and after the social events. It has been seen more common among women than their opposite sex as women react more intensely to emotional stimuli than men. Even though this review paper gave a unique glimpse on the association between social anxiety, drinking motives and alcohol use; the interaction between these variable with genders and alcohol-related components (as mentioned in the Alcohol Use Disorder Identification Test) are remaining complex and inconclusive. Future research is necessary to determine how this knowledge can be incorporated into prevention and intervention programs for the group at-risk.

Keywords: social anxiety, drinking motives, alcohol use

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1. INTRODUCTION

This review addresses the role of drinking motives in predicting alcohol use among normal and socially anxious population and its mediating effect in the relationship between social anxiety and alcohol use. Drinking becomes a trend when social fear becomes a threat to college students. Researchers framed social anxiety as social cognitive causes that might be related in proactive prosocial behavior; which refers to the self-serving social cognitive style, which means, of gaining something from doing something (Culotta & Goldstein, 2008), and attempting aggressive behavior. In such situation, alcohol has become the alternative mechanism that helps these people relax, or enjoy, or to just feel self-confident. Alcohol use does not happen by itself, unless it was motivated by internal and/or external mediator; drinking motives, which is best defined as the final decision to drink or not to drink and therefore the most proximal factor for engaging in drinking (Kuntsche, Knibbe, Gmel, & Engels, 2005). This mediator is considered as an adjacent factor predicting alcohol use compared to alcohol expectancies; which refers to the expectation placed upon drinking outcome, while drinking motives are the reasons to drink alcohol in achieving the outcome. A person with alcohol expectancies with a particular belief or expectation, for instance, alcohol relieves stress, would not necessarily consume alcohol for that reason; instead may drink to socialize in parties. On the other hand, drinking motives are the reasons that immediately motivate a person to drink to achieve a desired feeling. The paper begins with reviewing the prevalence of social anxiety and alcohol use, followed by the relationship between social anxiety and alcohol use. Although there are many intrinsic and extrinsic factors that predict alcohol use, the focus of this paper is placed on the most promising factor; drinking motives. The main scope of this study is to learn each mediator's effect in promoting drinking behavior, particularly among college students with different levels of social anxiety.

1.1 Prevalence of social anxiety

Social anxiety is a multidimensional phenomenon, which includes shyness, fear of discrimination, fear of negative evaluation, as well as rejection, social avoidance and distress (Puklek & Vidmar, 2000). Socially anxious people tend to underestimate themselves and make assumptions that their verbal and non-verbal action would be negatively evaluated and criticized by others (Kashdan & Steger, 2006). Thus these people were tending to avoid attending social situations where unpleasant emotions were provoked. According to Beesdo, Knappe, and Pine (2009), the onset age of the occurrence of social anxiety begins in late childhood throughout adolescence period which at times may continue to adulthood. Up to 3-4% of children and preadolescents too were reported to have social anxiety disorder (Alfano, Beidel, & Turner, 2006). Malaysian Psychiatric Association (MPA, 2006) statistically pointed that Social Anxiety Disorder is the third largest mental health problem following depression and alcohol dependence, globally. Across the world, seven out of a 100 people diagnosed with social anxiety disorder, and 13 out of a 100 people experience social anxiety at some time in their lives (Malaysian Psychiatric Association [MPA], 2006). This disorder is much common among women who were found to be more vulnerable to negative evaluations than men (Norberg, Norton, Olivier, & Zvolensky, 2010), however, the intensity of seeking treatment for social anxiety were seemed to be greater among males (Hofmann, Asnaani, & Hinton, 2010).

1.2 Prevalence of alcohol use among college students

Alcohol use continues to be a major concern among people as young as 15 years old (Ardiah, Zaidah, & Rokiah, 2009), and increases with age till it reaches the peak at 18-20 years old. Statistics indicated that the frequency of drinking alcohol may have its downturn as they grow older (NHMS, 2011). It has become a trend among college students for various reasons, including proneness to deviant

behavior (O'Leary-Barrett, Mackie, Castellanos-Ryan, Al-Khudhairi, & Conrod, 2010), sensation seeking, uncontrolled impulsivity (Ham & Hope, 2003), and as coping mechanism for stress, fear and depression. Problematic drinking among this age group is highly prevalent (Ham, Bonin, & Hope, 2007); reported 40 percent of college students experience "binge drinking"; a heavy drinking behavior that refers to consuming an average of more than two drinks per day, or more than 14 drinks per week; for men, and half of the stated frequency for women (National Institute on Alcohol Abuse and Alcoholism [NIAAA], n.d). National Health and Morbidity Survey (NHMS, 2011) forecasted that men drink 5.8% more in quantity than women; mostly involves students in their early 20s'. World Health Organization: Global Status Report on Alcohol (2004) reported 45% of Malaysian youths below the age of 18 consume alcohol regularly, and estimated that 30% of road accidents in Malaysia are caused by driving under alcohol intakes. However, there are inconsistent gender differences found in alcohol consumption. Men drink more often to display masculinity than women who drink on an emotional basis; and it appears that while both genders have similar vulnerabilities to alcohol and are subject to negative consequences, males have a higher tendency to carry more alcohol risk till adulthood (Schulte, Ramo, & Brown, 2009).

2. SOCIAL ANXIETY AND ALCOHOL USE

Alcohol use and social anxiety disorders can result in both significant physiological and psychological impairment, especially among individuals with comorbid diagnoses (Smith & Randall, 2012). The comorbidity of these disorders is among the five most prevalent mental disorders (Kessler et al., 2005; as cited in Schneier et al., 2010), and tend to co-occur at particularly high rates. The National Epidemiological Survey on Alcohol and Related Conditions found that 48% of individuals with a lifetime diagnoses of Social Anxiety Disorder [SAD] met criteria for Alcohol Use Disorder [AUD] at some point in their lives (Grant et al., 2004). Despite the belief that Social Anxiety Disorder and Alcohol Use Disorder tend to co-occur together or comorbid at some point of time, there appeared to be inconsistencies in statistically proving the positive relationships between social anxiety and alcohol use. For instance, in one study, social anxiety disorder demonstrated a positive relationship with alcohol use disorder (Lewis & O'Neill, 2000; Morris, Stewart, Theakston, & Mellings, 2004). In contrast, Ham & Hope (2005) found a negative relationship between these two variables. Nevertheless, no relationship at all was found between social anxiety and alcohol use by Eggleston, Woolaway-Bickel, and Schmidt (2004).

2.1 Drinking Motives

Alcohol is used by various people for various purposes; from enjoyment to medication. In this paper, it was believed that there would be a mediator that predicts alcohol use for a specific reason in relation to social fear; and this reasoning process is what labelled as the drinking motives. Cooper (1994) had proposed four specific drinking motives, namely; (i) enhancement motives which is internally generated positive reinforcement, (ii) coping motives which is internally generated negative reinforcement, (iii) social motives which is externally generated positive reinforcement, and (iv) conformity motives which is externally generated negative reinforcement (Stewart & Devine, 2000; Mushquash, Stewart, Comeau, & McGrath, 2008).

2.1.1 Enhancement Motives

Enhancement motives involve drinking to increase positive affect states or positive moods, such as sensation seeking and pleasurable motives (Ham & Hope, 2003). People who were internally motivated to drink to increase positive affect are more consistent on how much they drink across a drinking situation than those people with external motives. Enhancement motives are known as predictors of elevating alcohol use (Ham & Hope, 2003; Loxton, Bunker, Dingle, & Wong, 2015; Kenney, Paves, Grimaldi, & LaBrie, 2014) for both genders (Loxton, Bunker, Dingle, & Wong, 2015), mainly among men as reported by Van Damme et al. (2013). It becomes a social norm for men being the centre of the show in social

events, while women tend to keep up a low profile and focus more on developing interpersonal and/or intimate relationship with their close peers. Enhancement-motivated drinkers appeared to drink faster or swigged the drinks in few gulps; thus this motive causes frequent blackout, social or interpersonal consequences, which predicted heavy drinking among both genders (Merrill, & Read, 2010). Besides its contribution to alcohol frequency, enhancement motives too were found to be mediated by alcohol use and has tendency of alcohol-related problems (Read, Wood, Kahler, Maddock, & Palfai, 2003; Buckner, Schmidt, & Eggleston, 2006; Lewis et al., 2008; Van Damme et al., 2013); for instance, unsafe sex. Contrary to these findings, Ham, Zamboanga, Bacon, and Garcia (2009) argued that there was no significant relationship found between enhancement motives and hazardous drinking. Enhancement motives are often associated with those individuals who are extrovert, sensation-seekers and risk-seekers, highly impulsive, aggressive, have low inhibitory control and low responsibility, and a weak motivation to achieve (Kuntsche, Knibbe, Gmel, & Engels, 2006). Mezquita, Stewart, and Ruipérez (2010), similarly, stated that enhancement drinking motives were reported higher among extroverts' men whom were defined as carefree drinkers and were related to drinks per month. These drinkers may not be socially anxious individuals. Studies suggested that low social anxiety triggers large alcohol consumption through enhancement drinking motives (Ham et al., 2007; Clerkin & Barnett, 2012) compared to those of high social anxiety. In one study, there was no relationship reported between social anxiety and enhancement drinking motives (Blumenthal, Leen-Feldman, Frala, Bandour, & Ham, 2010).

2.1.2 *Social Motives*

Social motives, which are associated more towards normative drinking behavior, refer to drinking to achieve social affiliation to establish or maintain a good relationship or to attract the opposite sex. According to Stewart and Devine (2000), socially motivated drinkers tend to be outgoing individuals who used alcohol to get aligned with the social situations with peers. Like enhancement motives, social motives too were known for predicting more frequent drinking behavior, particularly among college students (Ham et al., 2007; Ham et al., 2009); however, it did not seem to increase the risk of problems resulting from drinking (Ham & Hope, 2003). Literatures suggested that social anxiety has a positive relationship with social motives, in which alcohol would be greatly consumed by socially anxious people (Schry & White, 2013) who are externally motivated to gain social affiliation in social events. This nature of connection applied for both genders (Labrie, Hummer, & Pedersen, 2007), which is contrary to recent studies that claimed men drink more on social, enhancement and conformity reasons and females drink for coping purposes (LaBrie, Ehret, Hummer, & Prenovost, 2011; Van Damme et al., 2013). Besides that, social motives too were seen correlating with all alcohol-related factors; total drinks, drinking days, average drinks per event, and heavy episodic drinking events, compared to the other two reasons in both men and women in both samples (LaBrie et al., 2007). Those individuals who are highly motivated to drink for social reasons are tend to be Extrovert, and have high Agreeableness to please others in surrounding, yet a low Intellect/ Imagination by which they failed to think wider on own and tend to follow their peers thoughts and beliefs to drink. These characteristics were seen higher among males; thus suggested that men drink more to obtain social rewards (Theakston, Stewart, Dawson, Knowlden-Loewen, & Lehman, 2004).

2.1.3 *Conformity Motives*

Conformity motives involve drinking to avoid the experience of social rejection, in which the desire to attain peer acceptance and social approval (Ham & Hope, 2003) creates room for an individual to drink. According to Cooper (1994), an individual has conformity motives to drink when there are strong peer pressures, especially among men who have greater self-consciousness thus choose to drink to avoid aversive consequences (Ham & Hope, 2003). It is the choice of going along or going alone, which generally falls back at going along as it is often adaptive (Griskevicius, Goldstein, Mortensen, Cialdini, & Kenrick, 2006). Socially anxious people who were afraid of negative evaluation or peer rejection were tending to drink more on conformity purposes; which shows that it is strongly related to social anxiety,

unlike enhancement and social motives (Buckner et al., 2006; Ham et al., 2007; Clerkin & Barnett, 2012; Schry & White, 2013). Apart from that, conformity motives and drinking in negative situations which were seen higher among women were found to be positively correlated with social anxiety (Norberg et al., 2010), contrary to Van Damme et al. (2013) who suggested men drinks more for conformity. Besides, conformity motives too, like enhancement motives, were found to be highly associated with alcohol-related problems (Cooper, 1994; Stewart et al., 2006). However, conformity motives predict less alcohol use compared to enhancement and social motives (Van Damme et al., 2013). Personality traits have never failed to influence an individual's drinking behavior and motives. Similar to social drinking motives, conformity drinking motives too are highly associated with low Intellect/Imagination, in which these individuals allowed others to think and decide for them. These individuals too were reported to have a high emotional stability thus prevent them to drink to suppress their negative feelings (Theakston et al., 2004).

2.1.4 *Coping Motives*

Coping motives involve drinking to avoid the experience of negative emotions such as depression or anxiety. This is the most potential mediator that lies between social anxiety and alcohol use. Several studies have found a significant positive relationship between these variables and a strong association with alcohol-related problems for high and moderate level of social anxiety (Ham et al., 2007; Martens et al., 2008; Clerkin & Barnett, 2012). Students, especially first year undergraduates, were among the most vulnerable group who often experience unpleasant feelings with their seniors and surroundings and able to drink more frequently to get rid of feeling depressed and stress (Lewis et al., 2008). In other word, it could refer to as drinking to cope with fear or stress, avoidance, or self-medication drinking (Ham & Hope, 2003). College students with higher levels of stress were seen to be highly motivated to drink to cope as a result of inability to restrain their behavior under stress (Corbin, Farmer, & Nolen-Hoekesma, 2013) which predicts the higher frequency of alcohol consumption as a mean to cope their negative emotions. Similar to enhancement motives, both coping-anxiety and coping-depression motives seem to be associated with greater drinking problems, and also psychological distress (Ham & Hope, 2003) compared to the effect of enhancement motives. However, both coping-anxiety and coping-depression were not falling under the same trait personality as suggested by Mezquita et al. (2010). Coping-anxiety drinking motives were significantly predicted by Low Conscientiousness and Neuroticism; whereas Neuroticism alone predicted coping-depression drinking motives (Mezquita et al., 2010). Besides being neurotic and having low conscientiousness, coping motives too was shown to have a low level of agreeableness, inferiority complex, and difficulties identifying and describing emotions, as well as being fearful of anxiety-related sensations (Kuntsche et al., 2006). The vulnerability of this motive appears to be stronger for women than men during the period in college, and vice versa when enters later life (Kuntschea et al., 2006). Although a couple of studies found no gender differences in coping motives (Van Damme et al., 2013), Hussong (2007) found that men were reported to drink sooner than women when encountered negative feelings, for instance, sadness. Yet, Hussong (2007) found it difficult to generalize these findings as the interaction between sex, motives and alcohol-related problems together prompt drinking behavior. Women high in both coping motives and alcohol-related problems were seen to drink sooner after a saddened event compared to women who had either and/or both variable in low state. Whereas for men, being high in alcohol-related problem did not prompt drinking behavior at the soonest, but with lower alcohol-related problems and any state of coping motives (Hussong, 2007; as cited in Littlefield, Talley, & Jackson, 2012). Besides, men were found to endorse all drinking motives more than women except coping motives (Ham et al., 2009).

2.2 *Self-Medication Model*

Initially described as Tension-Reduction Theory by Conger (1956) (Bolton, Cox, Clara, & Sareen, 2006), self-medication, is a common practice among socially anxious people. The literature has defined self-medication hypothesis as an act of seeking specific substances to eliminate negative

emotional states (Arendt et al., 2007), for instance, socially anxious people drink alcohol excessively to manage negative physiological and psychological states they experienced in social situations. Approximately 16.4% of the population who endorsed self-medication technique were social phobics (Bolton et al., 2006; Robinson, Sareen, Cox, & Bolton, 2009), particularly the first year undergraduates who experience plenty of depressive episodes and isolation (Mobach & Macaskill, 2011). The self-medication hypothesis is closely related to one of the prominent drinking motives proposed by Cooper (1994); which is coping motives. Studies literally found that drink-to-cope motives and self-medicate behavior shares a positive relationship, especially among the anxious population (Bolton, et al., 2006; Mobach & Macaskill, 2011). According to Mobach and Macaskill (2011), trait anxiety which refers to a general level of stress that is related to the personality of an individual and tendency to conditioned themselves to respond with an increase in state anxiety while anticipating a threatening situation that causes anxiety and stress (Tovilović, Novović, Mihić, & Jovanović, 2009) is more common among women compared to men; which Mobach and Macaskill (2011) evidently suggested that coping drinking motives have a significant positive correlation with trait anxiety and alcohol consumption among females. This nature of the relationship is contrary to state anxiety; a temporary condition in response to some experiences of unpleasant feelings (Tovilović et al., 2009) when confronted with specific situations, demands or a particular object or event, which is more common in men. Although gender differences are yet to be specified consistently by past literatures, there are reports claimed the existence of a significant relationship between coping motives, women and self-medication hypothesis (Mobach & Macaskill, 2011), while some researchers found that men endorsed alcohol more than women to cope with unpleasant feelings; thus females are less likely to be self-medicated compared to males (Bolton et al., 2006; Robinson et al., 2009) even though women scores higher in anxiety. On the other hand, men were seen to be highly endorsed self-medication, possibly due to tension reduction expectancies. This tension reduction theory was reported to mediate the relationship between negative life events and alcohol use of men, but not for women (Bolton et al., 2006).

3. CONCLUSION

This review sought to assist in integrating some of the inconsistent and mixed findings regarding the mediating role of drinking motives between social anxiety and alcohol use. Notwithstanding that some researchers had found there are not at all or a negative relationship present between social anxiety and alcohol use, the majority studies have shown that social anxiety is significantly positively correlated with alcohol use and a strong comorbidity exist between these two disorders. Both positively reinforcing drinking motives; enhancement and social motives, are positively related to frequency of alcohol consumption and predicts great alcohol-related problems due to excessive drinking. While socially anxious person drinks to socialize which may not impart positive social benefits, enhancement motives do not seem to associate with social anxiety. Any normal individual who wishes to increase positive mood chooses to drink alcohol in social situations. Studies found that those with low social anxiety who engaged in enhancement drinking are greater in number than social-motivated people with high social anxiety who control their drinking quantity to avoid getting embarrassed or being negatively evaluated. Thus, enhancement drinking contributes to more alcohol-related problems compared to social drinking motives.

Understanding the coping and conformity as essential factors in social anxiety, more studies have been done specifically into finding the gradual effects of these motives in alcohol use, such as drinking frequency and problems. Drinking-to-cope with emotional pain or fear associates greatly with women more than men. The desire to attain peer acceptance and social approval has been identified as the major reason for alcohol use. Unlike coping, conformity motives seem to appear higher among men than women who choose to drink to avoid aversive external consequences such as social embarrassment among male peers in social situations (Stewart, Zvolensky, & Eifert, 2001). In addition, literatures supported that

socially anxious people who drink for coping and conformity purposes are particularly vulnerable to come into contact with the negative consequences of consuming alcohol.

Overall, these literatures offers a brief understanding into how people with and without social anxiety differ in their reactions to events that challenges their social image. Even though this review paper gave a unique glimpse on the association between social anxiety, drinking motives and alcohol use; the interaction between these variable with genders and alcohol-related components are remaining complex and inconclusive. Future research is necessary to determine how this knowledge can be incorporated into prevention and intervention programs for the at-risk group of people.

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